

The Economic and Operational Impacts of Truck Idle Time: A Study in a Sugarcane Sector Company

Os Impactos Econômicos e Operacionais do Tempo de Motor Ocioso em Caminhões: Um estudo em uma Empresa do Setor Canavieiro
Los Impactos Económicos y Operativos del Tiempo de Motor en Marcha en Camiones: Un Estudio en una Empresa del Sector Cañero

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Abstract: Sugarcane transport in Brazil requires high logistical efficiency, with engine idling time being a critical factor in fuel waste and operational costs. This study aims to analyze the average engine idling time in a fleet of 20 trucks from a sugar-alcohol plant in the interior of São Paulo, assessing its economic and operational impacts. The research is descriptive with a quantitative approach, using onboard telemetry data from 2022 to 2025. Results show that between 2022 and 2024, approximately 12% of engine-on time was idle, equivalent to 48 hours/month per truck, causing unnecessary consumption of 154 liters of diesel per month. With the implementation of telemetry, driver training, and operational adjustments in 2025, the idling percentage decreased to 7.3%, resulting in a potential annual savings of 17,000 liters of diesel. It is concluded that monitoring and managing engine idling time significantly reduce costs, improve operational efficiency, and lower environmental impact, confirming the research objective.

Keywords: Fuel consumption; Fleet performance; Onboard telemetry.

Resumo: O transporte de cana-de-açúcar no Brasil demanda elevada eficiência logística, sendo o tempo de motor ocioso um fator crítico de desperdício de combustível e custos operacionais. Este estudo tem como objetivo analisar o tempo médio de motor ocioso em uma frota de 20 caminhões de uma usina sucroalcooleira do interior de São Paulo, avaliando seus impactos econômicos e operacionais. A pesquisa é descritiva, com abordagem quantitativa, utilizando dados de telemetria embarcada entre 2022 e 2025. Os resultados indicam que, entre 2022 e 2024, aproximadamente 12% do tempo de motor ligado era ocioso, equivalente a 48 horas/mês por caminhão, gerando consumo desnecessário de 154 litros de diesel mensais. Com a implementação de telemetria, treinamentos e ajustes operacionais em 2025, o percentual caiu para 7,3%, com economia potencial de 17 mil litros de diesel/ano. Conclui-se que o monitoramento e gestão do tempo de motor ocioso contribuem significativamente para redução de custos, eficiência operacional e menor impacto ambiental, confirmando o alcance do objetivo proposto.

Palavras-chave: Consumo de combustível; Desempenho de frota; Telemetria embarcada.

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Resumen: El transporte de caña de azúcar en Brasil requiere alta eficiencia logística, siendo el tiempo de motor en ralentí un factor crítico de desperdicio de combustible y costos operativos. Este estudio tiene como objetivo analizar el tiempo promedio de motor en ralentí en una flota de 20 camiones de una planta azucarera y de etanol en el interior de São Paulo, evaluando sus impactos económicos y operativos. La investigación es descriptiva, con enfoque cuantitativo, utilizando datos de telemetría embarcada entre 2022 y 2025. Los resultados indican que, entre 2022 y 2024, aproximadamente el 12% del tiempo de motor encendido era inactivo, equivalente a 48 horas/mes por camión, generando un consumo innecesario de 154 litros de diésel mensuales. Con la implementación de telemetría, capacitación de conductores y ajustes operativos en 2025, el porcentaje se redujo al 7,3%, con un ahorro potencial de 17.000 litros de diésel al año. Se concluye que el monitoreo y la gestión del tiempo de motor en ralentí contribuyen significativamente a la reducción de costos, mayor eficiencia operativa y menor impacto ambiental, confirmando el cumplimiento del objetivo de la investigación.

Palabras clave: Consumo de combustible; Rendimiento de flota; Telemetría embarcada.

1. INTRODUCTION

According to the National Supply Company (CONAB) (2023), Brazil is the world's largest producer of sugarcane and is among the main exporters of sugar and ethanol. In the 2022/23 harvest, production exceeded 610 million tons, moving thousands of trucks daily between fields, mills, and distribution centers. This high volume of transport implies strong logistical demand, whose performance directly affects the sector's competitiveness (CONAB, 2023). As highlighted by Nicolau, Chaves, and Zanchetta (2020), the fleet of road vehicles in Brazil has a direct impact on energy consumption and carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions, with this effect being more significant than the impact of infrastructure investments or the composition of the fuel matrix.

In this context, idle engine time in heavy trucks emerges as a highly relevant factor. According to Valeretto (2018), monitoring each vehicle's fuel consumption individually enables the identification of usage patterns, facilitating the implementation of strategies to reduce diesel costs. Furthermore, according to the author, in some operations, idle engine time can represent between 10% and 15% of the fleet's total fuel consumption. This percentage, when expanded to large operations, results in significant financial losses and a considerable increase in gas emissions into the environment. In addition, as Nicolau, Chaves, and Zanchetta (2020) observe, prolonged engine operation without load accelerates wear on mechanical components, reducing vehicle lifespan and increasing preventive and corrective maintenance costs.

In the sugarcane sector, this situation is exacerbated by the nature of operations. Françoso et al. (2017) highlight that trucks remain for long periods at loading lines, weighing scales, and unloading yards, often with the engine running. The distance between the farm and the processing plant directly influences harvesting and transportation costs, reinforcing the importance of operational planning (Françoso et al., 2017). Thus, engine idle time translates into wasted fuel, additional pollutant emissions, and increased operating costs.

According to CONAB (2023), sugarcane plays a strategic role in the Brazilian energy matrix, not only for producing sugar and ethanol but also for the socioeconomic impact of its production chain. Furthermore, as highlighted by Nicolau, Chaves and Zanchetta (2020), the logistical challenges of road transport directly influence the sector's costs, operational efficiency, and sustainability.

Given this scenario, the analysis of engine idle time in sugarcane trucks proves relevant in three main dimensions: economic, due to the high cost of diesel in logistics; operational, due to the impact on fleet performance and equipment lifespan; and environmental, due to its contribution to increased CO₂ emissions in a sector that seeks alignment with sustainability practices and a low-carbon economy. In this context, understanding the magnitude of this problem and proposing mitigating strategies is essential to strengthening the competitiveness and sustainability of the sugarcane energy sector.

In this sense, the objective of this article, through descriptive research with a quantitative approach, is to analyze the average engine idle time in a fleet of 20

trucks used to transport sugarcane at a sugar and ethanol plant in the interior of São Paulo, based on onboard telemetry data from the years 2022, 2023, 2024, and 2025. The aim is to evaluate the economic and operational impacts of this idle time, identify its causes, and verify measures to reduce it that promote greater logistical efficiency and sustainability in the sugar and ethanol sector.

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

2.1 Idle engine and its impact on operational efficiency

According to Valeretto (2018), idling is defined as the engine running when the vehicle is not in motion. Although often considered harmless, this condition generates fuel consumption without delivering useful work, contributing to significant waste in logistics operations.

Furthermore, Nicolau, Chaves and Zanchetta (2020) highlight that in heavy trucks, fuel consumption at idle can range from 1 to 3 liters per hour, depending on engine power, vehicle age and environmental conditions.

Furthermore, Françoso et al. (2017) highlight that in the transportation of agricultural cargo, such as sugarcane, engine idle time tends to be high due to sector-specific characteristics, including queues at loading areas, waiting time at weighbridges, and delays in unloading at mills.

From an energy-efficiency perspective, idling time is considered an indicator of operational inefficiency, as it consumes resources without generating value. Consequently, this factor directly affects companies' competitiveness, especially in sectors with low added value per ton transported, such as sugarcane (Nicolau, Chaves, Zanchetta, 2020).

2.2 Economic and environmental impacts of idling engines

According to Valeretto (2018), diesel consumption accounts for 40% to 50% of the operational costs of road transport fleets, and fleet management, combined with driver training, is essential to reduce these expenses.

As highlighted by CONAB (2023), for sugarcane trucks, each hour of idling can generate considerable fuel costs, not accounting for depreciation and additional engine maintenance. Therefore, reducing engine idle time contributes to significant financial savings (Valeretto, 2018).

Additionally, Gonçalves and Lima (2021) point out that engine wear during idle is not negligible, as prolonged idling increases internal engine carbon buildup, reducing efficiency and necessitating earlier maintenance, thereby increasing total ownership costs.

Furthermore, as Nicolau, Chaves, and Zanchetta (2020) point out, diesel, as a fossil fuel, contributes to emissions of CO₂, CO, and particulate matter, affecting not only the environment but also the health of nearby communities. Additionally, Valeretto (2018) highlights that for every liter of diesel burned, approximately 2.64 kg of CO₂ are emitted into the atmosphere. The average fuel

waste in sugarcane trucks, therefore, represents a significant source of greenhouse gas emissions.

In this context, Nicolau, Chaves and Zanchetta (2020) observe that public policies and environmental regulations have been demanding greater energy efficiency in the transport sector, pressuring companies to adopt practices to reduce engine idle time.

2.3 Strategies for reducing engine idle time

According to Valeretto (2018), driver training is an effective strategy, as raising driver awareness can significantly reduce idling time, promoting operational efficiency and cost reduction.

Furthermore, Nicolau, Chaves and Zanchetta (2020) suggest that establishing operational goals and rewarding drivers for better performance encourage fuel-economy practices.

Valeretto (2018) also highlights that monitoring technologies, such as telemetry systems and embedded IoT, enable real-time identification of engine idle time, providing data to support efficient fleet management.

Finally, automatic shutdown technologies that deactivate the engine when there is no movement, when implemented, allow trucks to turn off the engine after a certain period of inactivity, reducing fuel waste and gas emissions. Consequently, these practices, when combined, contribute to cost reduction, decreased emissions, increased engine lifespan, and greater logistical efficiency in agricultural operations (Nicolau; Chaves; Zanchetta, 2020).

3. METHOD

According to Gil (2019), the present research is characterized as descriptive and quantitative, as it seeks to analyze, measure, and interpret data on engine idle time in trucks used to transport sugarcane. Thus, descriptive studies allow observation, recording, and analysis of facts without directly interfering with them, an essential characteristic for this work (Gil, 2019).

3.1 Unit of analysis, sample and data collection

The unit of analysis corresponds to heavy trucks used in sugarcane transportation operations at a large sugarcane and ethanol production/processing plant in the interior of São Paulo. Data from 20 vehicles were evaluated over 30 consecutive days. Therefore, the results consistently reflect the behavior of the fleet studied.

It is worth highlighting that the information was obtained through embedded telemetry systems, which record parameters such as:

- Engine running time;
- Idle time/idling (engine running without movement);
- Distance traveled;

- Fuel consumption.

According to research, these systems enable greater accuracy in data collection and reduce the risk of errors arising from perceptual or manual recordings.

The data used covers the years 2022, 2023, 2024, and 2025, allowing for historical and comparative analysis of average engine idle time. Figure 1 illustrates the telemetry equipment installed on a truck's dashboard, showing how data is captured in real time for operational efficiency analysis.

Figure 1 – Telemetry equipment installed on the dashboard of a truck.

Source: Research data (2025).

The device, integrated with the truck's sensors, records parameters in real time, such as engine running time, idle time, fuel consumption, and distance traveled, allowing for data collection for operational efficiency analysis.

3.2 Indicators analyzed

To analyze the impact of engine idle time, the following indicators were defined:

- Percentage of Engine Idle Time (PMO): represents the ratio between the time the engine remains idle and the total engine running time, allowing the evaluation of the fleet's operational efficiency, as presented in formulas (1).

$$PMO = \frac{\text{Tempo ocioso}}{\text{Tempo total do motor ligado}} * 100 \quad (1)$$

- Average Daily Engine Idle Time (ADIT): calculated as the number of idling hours divided by the total number of days in the analysis period, providing a daily measure of fuel waste, as detailed in formula (2).

$$TMDO = \frac{\text{Tempo ocioso}}{\text{Dias avaliados}} \quad (2)$$

3.3 Study limitations

Some limitations of this research should be highlighted, such as the sample

being restricted to 20 trucks, which may not reflect the reality of all operations, and the omission of external factors such as temperature, topography, and fleet age, which can influence consumption.

Despite these limitations, the data obtained provides a consistent overview of the impacts of idling engines on sugarcane transportation, allowing for reliable economic, environmental, and operational analyses. Therefore, overcoming these limitations, the results presented below allow for a consistent assessment of the economic and operational impacts of idling engines on the analyzed fleet.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To analyze engine idle time, i.e., time spent running without acceleration, in a fleet of 20 trucks used to transport sugarcane, onboard telemetry data was collected from 2022 to 2024, with 2025 serving as a reference year for implementing an improvement process.

It is worth noting that these values are averages calculated for the 20 trucks in the fleet, based on behavior observed from 2022 to 2024.

During the analyzed period, from 2022 to 2024, it was found that each truck has a monthly availability of 720 hours (30 days × 24 hours), of which, on average, 400 hours correspond to the engine being on — accounting for idle and acceleration time — while 320 hours are off. This average of 400 hours was calculated based on data collected between 2022, 2023, and 2024 from the 20 trucks in the fleet.

Similarly, the average engine idle time found was approximately 48 hours per month per truck, which is equivalent to 12% of the period in which the engine is running without acceleration, as calculated by Formula (1) for PMO: $PMO = \frac{\text{Tempo ocioso}}{\text{Tempo total do motor ligado}} * 100 = \frac{48 \text{ horas}}{400 \text{ horas}} * 100 = 12\%$ (3)

PMO indicates the proportion of time the engine runs without producing movement. Translating this value into daily terms, TMDO corresponds to approximately 1.6 hours per day, or 96 minutes per truck, according to formula (2), representing a loss of operational efficiency and wasted fuel. The TMDO calculation was performed considering the average monthly engine idle time per truck:

$$TMDO = \frac{\text{Tempo ocioso}}{\text{Dias avaliados}} = \frac{48 \text{ horas}}{30 \text{ dias}} = 1,6 \text{ horas por dia ou } 96 \text{ minutos} \quad (4)$$

The research found that idle engine time must be continuously monitored, as each hour the truck remains running without moving represents fuel loss, engine wear, and increased operating costs. Based on this data, the organization identified the need to implement fleet management improvements to reduce idling time and optimize operational efficiency.

4.1 Consolidated Results and Economic Indicators

Based on average data collected over 36 months (2022 to 2024), the main indicators of engine idle time for a fleet of 20 trucks used for sugarcane transportation were consolidated. This data allows for the creation of operational efficiency metrics and the estimation of the economic impact of fuel waste.

The TMDO per truck was approximately 48 hours per month, equivalent to 12% of the period in which the engine was running without acceleration. Thus, to estimate the fuel consumption associated with this time, the average diesel consumption rate at idle recorded in the trucks was considered, which was 3.20 liters/hour. From the following relationship, according to formula (3):

$$\text{Fuel consumption at idle (L/month)} = \text{Average engine idle time (h/month)} \times \text{Average diesel consumption (liters/ hour)} \quad (4)$$

Replacing the average values:

$$\text{Fuel consumption during idling (L/month)} = 48 \text{ hours/month} * 3.2 \text{ liters/hour} = 154 \text{ liters per truck.}$$

To summarize the results, Table 1 presents the average indicators obtained for each truck in the fleet, including engine running time, engine idle time, percentage of idle time, and associated fuel consumption.

Based on these values, it is possible to estimate the economic impact of engine idle time considering the entire fleet and the period analyzed:

$$154 \text{ liters/month} \times 36 \text{ months} \times \text{R\$ } 5.90 \times 20 \text{ trucks} = \text{R\$ } 654,192.00$$

Table 1 – Average idle engine indicators for the fleet (2022–2024), consolidated values per truck.

Indicator	Values obtained
Time available for work	720 hours/month
Total engine running time	400 hours/month
Average engine idle time during the period	48 hours/month
Percentage of engine idling	12%
Fuel consumption while idling	154 liters/month

Source: research data (2025).

These results show that the percentage of idle engine time represents a significant waste of fuel, directly impacting fleet operating costs and underscoring the need to implement measures to reduce idle time, improve logistical efficiency, and conserve resources.

It is well known that this monetary amount could have been reinvested in telemetry technology, driver training programs, and preventive fleet maintenance. Medeiros et al. (2024) show that companies that adopt efficiency-focused management are able not only to reduce costs but also to improve their

competitiveness and sustainability. Furthermore, direct fuel savings would increase companies' competitive margins and reduce total logistics costs.

4.2 Evolution of Engine Idle Time and Reduction Measures – 2025 Crop Year

Based on data collected in previous years, the company implemented a fleet management system focused on reducing engine idle time, establishing an initial target of 6.50% idle time per truck by the end of the 2025 harvest season. This target equates to approximately 26 hours of engine idle time per month, based on a theoretical monthly availability of 400 hours with the engine running (parameters derived from the last 3 years).

To achieve this reduction, several strategic actions were adopted:

- Real-time monitoring via onboard telemetry identifies each truck's idling periods and generates automatic alerts when idle time approaches the defined limit.
- Driver training and development: focusing on good operating practices, turning off the engine during waiting periods, and efficient driving.
- Operational planning for loading queues and unloading yards: reducing waiting times and reorganizing internal logistics to minimize the time the truck remains idling.
- Use of automatic shutdown technologies, which stop the engine from running when the vehicle remains inactive for a certain period of time.

The evolution of TMDO during the 2025 harvest season, from April to August, is presented and monitored in Table 2, based on the average across the 20 trucks in the fleet.

Table 2 - Results of Reducing Idle Engine Time in the Fleet – 2025 Crop Year

Month - 2025	Average TMDO	PMO (%)	Observations
April	1.86 hours – 112 minutes	14.0%	begins the driver adaptation period.
May	1.8 hours – 108 minutes	13.5%	Adjustments to loading planning and practical training.
June	1 hour and 44 minutes – 86 minutes	10.8%	Introduction of automatic shutdown
July	1 hour, 23 minutes – 74 minutes	9.2%	Reducing queues in loading areas and optimizing routes.
August	0.97 hours – 58.4 minutes	7.3%	Target close to being achieved – 6.5% – constant monitoring.

Source: research data (2025).

It is observed that, throughout the 2025 harvest season, the implementation of management measures resulted in a significant decrease in engine idle time. The idle time between months (IPM) decreased from 14.0% in April to 7.3% in August, indicating that the company is close to achieving the 6.5% target for the period. This reduction represents not only an advance in operational efficiency but also a significant change in driver behavior and the use of fleet management support technologies.

To measure the practical impact of this reduction, Table 3 compares idle/non-revving fuel consumption in the average scenario for 2022–2024 (12% PMO) with the projected target of 6.5% PMO for 2025, including the potential savings in liters of fuel and in financial value.

Comparative analysis shows that if the 6.5% target is achieved, the company could save approximately 17,000 liters of diesel per year, representing about R\$ 100,000 annually in operational fuel costs. In addition to the direct reduction in expenses, continuous monitoring of engine idle time contributes to less mechanical wear, longer equipment lifespan, and better utilization of the fleet's logistical capacity. Therefore, the adopted management practice demonstrates a positive impact on both economic performance and operational efficiency, establishing itself as a strategic differentiator for the company.

Table 3 – Comparison of idle engine consumption (2022-2024) vs. current situation (2025).

Indicator	Current situation (12% PMO – 2022 to 2024)	Target (6.5% PMO – 2025)	Potential Economy
Average monthly TMDO (hours/truck)	48 hours/month	26 hours/month	22 hours/month
Monthly consumption (liters/truck)	154 liters	83 liters	71 liters
Total monthly consumption (20 trucks)	3,080 liters	1,660 liters	1,420 liters
Total annual consumption (20 trucks)	36,960 liters	19,920 liters	17,040 liters
Total annual consumption (R\$ 5.90/liter)	R\$ 218,060.00/year	R\$ 117,520.00/year	R\$ 100,540.00/year

Source: research data (2025).

5. CONCLUSION

The results obtained clearly show that controlling engine idle time is a decisive factor in reducing costs and increasing efficiency in sugarcane transportation. Throughout 2022 to 2024, it was observed that, on average, 12% of engine idling time was spent without generating movement, resulting in wasted fuel and increased vehicle wear. From the 2025 harvest onwards, with the use of

telemetry, training, and operational adjustments, this rate began to fall consistently, approaching the target of 6.5%. In addition to saving more than 17,000 liters of diesel per year, the process yielded benefits including improved logistical organization, reduced environmental impact, and a longer fleet lifespan.

Thus, the study's objective was fully achieved. The analysis of engine idle time in a fleet of 20 trucks, based on telemetry data from 2022 to 2025, enabled not only measuring the economic and operational impacts but also proposing practical ways to reduce the problem. The results show that it is possible to transform real-time information into strategic decisions that increase the company's competitiveness.

However, it is important to note that the research focused on a single fleet and did not consider external factors, such as terrain, climate, or truck age, which also influence fuel consumption. Future studies could expand the sample, including environmental variables, and even test the use of other technologies to predict and correct inefficiencies before they occur.

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